

Setting Device In Mulk Raj Anand's Short Stories

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Abstract

As a writer Anand's avowed aim has been to relieve man of his burden—to help him evolve through his suffering to become the “whole man”. As “folklore is integral to the life-pattern of a people”, in it he finds answers to questions of human predicament arising from a variety of factors: a rigid pattern of relationships, widowhood, casteism, classism, faulty texture of education and man's petty foibles. Anand has been thoroughly acquainted with the folk tale form and despite its simplicity has found it highly communicative. This convinced him that the story form could serve well in his humanistic needs.

Anand follows the pattern of the folk tale to build up the plot of his own stories. He exercises utmost economy in the use of action, yet successfully deals with situations affecting his fellow brethren. To illustrate, he builds up the whole super-structure of *The Barber's Trade Union* on the mere hunch of a barber boy to dress like an English Sahib. As this invites censure from his high-caste Hindu customers the boy himself strikes down work and turns the tables on his tormentors.

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The two forms of short story that particularly influenced Anand are the folk and the fable. As every Indian during his childhood is nourished on the ancient tale, it is deeply rooted in Indian metabolism. Although the contemporary short story writer has been deeply influenced by the development of the genre in the West, for him the prototype remains to be his own epics and mythological stories.

I read it at an early age and was inspired by it to read and hear man of the folk tales told in my country I wanted to write stories as finished in form and as rich in content as the stories told among my people. In fact, the folk tale form had seemed to me the most perfect of short story, says Anand True to its name *Kathasaritsagar* (The Ocean of Stories) is the largest single collection of short stories in the world. Conceived as originally devised by Lord Shiva to entertain his consort, the authorship of the stories is attributed to Somadeva, to the latter half of the eleventh century. The stories included in the monumental work are the tales of adventure dealing with the romantic love against the background of the fantastic and the supernatural. Often the character depicted here face unusual situations and cross into the supernatural realms of the embodied voices, black magic demons and even gods. The virtuous, however, emerge triumphant and the stories end on a happy note.

A fine specimen of the *Kathasaritsagar* story is 'Which is the Wickeder Sex? It is related by the parrot, Vidyachaudamani to prove to the maina, Somica, that the female sex is sickeder. The story has for its central character Vasudatta who develops illicit relationship with a handsome bought and has many clandestine meetings with him. Once as her

paramour is waiting for her, the city guards mistake him for being a fugitive and put him to death. Soon afterwards a goblin takes possession of the dead body and bits off Vasudatta's nose when she is later sitting beside it. Vasudatta accuses her husband of having a ill treated her. For proof, she has her bitten nose to show to the king. But just when the man is about to be executed, a thief, the only witness to the whole sequence of events gives his testimony and secures his release. The course of events culminating in the climax is presented thus:

But the lover had been surprised by the city guards, taken for a runaway thief, and put to death. His body dangled from a tree and there was a halter round his neck. Vasudatta was distracted, but only for a while. She lowered her paramour's body and, hoping that he might still be alive, adorned it with flowers and perfumes. Even though he was senseless she embraced him, so completely was her mind blinded by passion. Meanwhile a goblin had taken possession of the corpse and he suddenly bit off Vasudatta's nose. Convinced that her lover was indeed dead, and suffering great pain, she slowly made her way to her own apartment. The thief who had watched the entire sequence of events was shocked, 'Will woman's wickedness admit no limit?' he reflected I wonder what she will do now.

This passage has all the characteristics of a typical *Kathasaritsagar* story. For theme, it has romantic love-affair, and for background, an invisible goblin who takes possession of the lover's dead body. The spirit advances the course of events as Vasudatta, on returning home, accuses her husband of having shown utmost cruelty to her. The thief, a witness to the whole sequence of events,

arouses the readers curiosity to know what the woman would do next.

However, what lends Kathasaritsagar a perennial appeal is a down-to-earth realistic portrayal of its characters. Characteristically, the supernatural background does not divest men and women of their essential human traits. Their powerful delineation bears evidence to the fact that its author had a firm grounding in reality and was well versed in human psychology. The men and women, inhabiting the authors world of fantasy, display such basic human aspirations and feelings as are the common lot of all persons. To illustrate:

There was a woman who had only one son, she desired to have another. A witch suggest that if she sacrificed the one son she had to the gods, she would be blessed with another. The woman was about to carry out the suggestion when an old woman chided her and asked her to be happy with the one existing son rather than desire the one who may not after all be born, meanwhile losing even the one she had.

Besides the folk or popular tale typified best Kathasaritsagar, Anand was influenced by another form of the ancient Indian tale, namely, the fable. Though the term has been applied originally to every imaginative tale, it is confined in modern use to short stories, either in prose or verse, which inculcate a moral lesson in a pleasant grab. Dr. Samuel Johnson's definition of the term has a wide application in the context of the classical Sanskrit. For him, fable is: "a narrative in which beings irrational, and sometimes inanimate, are for the purpose of moral instruction feigned to act and speak worth human interests and passions." The introduction of irrational being for the purpose of moral edification is a skilful artistic device. A direct reference to man's merits and demerits may not be as palatable to man as it is through the agency of irrational beings veneered with common sense, human interests and passions. Moreover, the presence of simple delectation is rooted in human psychology itself. Man has ever delighted in his association with the animal and has watched his activities with keen interest. Besides, human passions, emotions, desired and ambitions are attributable to the lower worlds, even to the material as is stated in New Popular Encyclopedia:

The satisfaction which we derive from fables does not lies wholly in the pleasure that we receive from the symbolic representation but lies deeper in the feeling that the order of nature is the same in the spiritual and the material world. (Encyclopedia, p.291.)

The form is best illustrated by the Panchatantra which is universally acknowledged as a collection of the ancient Indian fables.

Designed to give lessons in practical wisdom, the Panchatantra presumes that the purpose of all life is to attain happiness with dogged effort, wit, wisdom and resourcefulness. Real life is not always edifying. The world is full of unscrupulous people. To deal with them, to encounter chicanery, artifice and pretence, one has to be shrewd realistic and free from sentimentality. The Crow and the Snake illustrates the point. Once, a black snake starts killing the chicks of a crow couple who have made their nest on a lower branch of a huge bunyan tree. After the couple has lost many of their young ones the crow seeks guidance from his clever friend, jackal. Then, acting on his friends advice, they steal a golden chain belonging to a woman of king's court and deposit it in the snake-pit. Later, as the kings men search the burrow with their sticks, the snake comes out. The soldiers kills the snake, recover the chain and return. The story shows that with wisdom and clever device a person can defeat even his formidable enemies.

As the objective of the Panchatantra fable is to give moral lessons, they incorporate passage containing philosophy, catchy verses and pithy sayings. Their introduction makes the moral maxims or practical truths palatable. Here is a sample from the The Rabit Who outlived a Lion: "A cow must not be milked every hour, but only in morning. Remember that the loss of his subjects is also the kings loss. Here is yet another to emphasise that one should not create ill-will: "One must never make an enemy for nothing, even if he is harmless. After all, we do not take poison just because there is a doctor in the locality The plot of a typical Panchatantra tale emphasizes the use of suspense. To arouse the readers curiosity and to preserve it tale after tale, the writers makes use of racy narration, as in the following extract from 'The Servants Revenge':

When the banquet was over, he regaled them with gifts and escorted the king back to the palace. When the party reached the palace, the merchant discovered one of the kings domestics, a man called Vrishbha, comfortable seated at a prominent place. He hastened to catch hold of the impudent fellow and drove his out of the hall. From that moment Vrishbha vowed vengeance against the merchant.

The author of the Panchatantra also uses the device of telling a tale within a tale. The work consists of five books: The Loss of Friends, The Winning of Friends, Crows and Owls, Loss of Gains and III-Considered Action. Each volume has a framing story containing numerous others. The story 'Disruption of Friendship' included in Book 1 is a good illustration of this technique. The Jackal Kartaka, offers to bring to his masters presence, the bull, Sanjivaka, in who is loud bellowing, the lion, Pingalka, fears threat to his royal authority. To Sanjivaka, the clever jackal promises safe conduct

on the condition that they will both enjoy power and wealth at the king's cost. As a precaution against any future betrayal by the king, he relates the tale of the merchant, Vajradanta. He thus suggests that one should not be arrogant towards royal retainers.

The fable form is also exemplified in the Aesop's fables and the Jataka Tales. The Aesopian fables too are stories of wisdom, though they are a little tragic in tenor. Didactic in nature, they usually have a double meaning. As they reflect the ideals or ordinary people about the conduct of life, they are a popular genre. The fable recommends social virtues which are meant to teach worldly wisdom. For example, in the story *The Fox and the Crow*, the crow that holds a piece of meat in his beak is told by the clever fox that he sings sweeter than a nightingale. No sooner does the crow open his mouth to sing than the piece falls down from his beak. The clever fox picks it up and goes away. The fable suggests that the stupid, the innocent and the credulous are devoured first, and even the kindest treatment cannot tame a savage nature. The fables teach us practical wisdom and the safest way to live in the world. They even teach us that we should not mind our failures. The fox who said, "Who cares for sour grapes?" will ever be quoted by those who choose to justify their failures in life.

The Jataka tales are more akin to the Panchatantra stories, for they too stress the need to be virtuous. The Buddha goes to enlightenment for the merit he attained through many past lives. Later, to facilitate the task of teaching his disciples, he related to them the episodes from his previous births. The obvious purpose here is moral edification. The collection of these episodes is *Jataka Tales*. The Jataka stories too are didactic in nature. The moral tone keeps on changing its pitch. Of the large treasure-house of the Jatakas, we have stories dealing exclusively with grave issues of right and wrong; stories serving as a warning against excessive talkativeness, or indulging in wordy disputes. A few of these deal with some ordinary problem of life.

The combined characteristics of the folk tale and the fable form are Anand's stick in trade to build up his own short stories. His reliance on them makes his contemporary stories "a tribute of the current to the source." He retells them in the two anthologies *Indian Fairy Tales* (1946), and *More Indian Fairy Tales* (1961). He acknowledges his deep gratitude to these tales by going back to which he could evolve a pattern for the contemporary short story.

Through this sample, native organisation of the story Anand denounces casteism. He brings to Chandu, the barber boy laurels of victory by caricaturing the orthodox Hindus with their shabby, long, unkempt beards. The fact that the protagonist is illiterate and is without any specific complexity

does not stop him from having a last laugh at the perpetrators of casteism. Here is the sorry state to which they are brought as a result of Chandu's strike. And it was said that at last the landlord's wife threatened to run away with somebody, because being younger than her husband by twenty years, she had borne with him as long as he kept himself in trim, but was now disgusted with him beyond the limits of reconciliation. (*The Barbers Trade Union*, p. 15.)

Likewise, in *The Price of Bananas* Anand satirizes a rich but miserly merchant who grudges even a few annas to the vendor who has retrieved his cap from the monkeys. Anand does this by getting a caricature of the Seth drawn by the narrator in which is shown supplicating to the monkey who had taken his cap away.

Built on the theme of casteism *A Cock and Bull Story* has even a simpler organisation. The story brings into focus two adversaries a Brahmin of the dhobi bull-caste, Amru, and a dhobi of the cock-caste, Chetu- by a stream in space. Amru wants to go across the wooden log first by dint of his superior caste but finds a strong adversary in Chetu who blocks his way. The result is a head-on collision and the fall of both of them into the stream. Amru dies, whereas Chetu is taken out and restored to life.

One, however, need not take the improbable situation in the story at its face value as Anand has merely devised it to denounce casteism to show the hazards of using force to remove untouchability. The outcome of the clash is even more than the head-on collision of the representatives of the two castes in significant. Though, the use of the force takes its toll from the low-caste. Chetu too, it results in the death of Amru alone. The ending of the story thus stresses the need for the use of non-violent means to put an end to casteism. It fully endorses Gandhi's view that right end must come through right means only.

Anand assimilates and retains the basic forms of the ancient folk tale and seeks to adapt it to the twentieth century. Knowing the modern readers' path to direct moralizing he places didacticism by a couple of modes constituting the folk idiom viz., generalizations of truth, theology and philosophy. In the *Lottery*; for instance, he employs the old fable form to convey man's secret yearning to become rich overnight. He concludes it thus with a kind of universal generalisation:

Anand's experimentation with the ancient Indian folk form does not end with the retention or alternation of its essential features. It goes beyond to take in neo-psychology, the disintegration of the modern mind. The writer seeks to modernize, "to adapt to the twentieth century the rich Indian tradition of the bardic recital." His stories are, therefore, rooted in motivation and a psychological

analysis of his characters. Three of his stories are psycho-analytical studies of characters of a young expectant mother (The Tamarind Tree), a sexually frigid house wife (The Silver Bangles) and an infatuated youth (The Thief).

The authors employs several devices to present a psychological study. In *The Tamarind Tree*, Roopa, an expectant mother, has a highly potent stimulus in the ripe tamarind fruit to activate her mind, to start in it a chain reaction of associated ideas. Motivated by hunger she focuses her mind on the tamarind fruit and is filled with the desire "to put on the rich, ripe colour of the tamarind fruit on her lips." This brings to her mind the thought of her clever husband who does not miss a single opportunity of having physical contact with her. "Perhaps, 'They' would come home from the office and tease her..." At this juncture, the arrival of her husband, as if in answer to her thoughts gives her mind the expected push. An eager husband tells his wife, "Come hurry, not so many 'blandishments'." This naturally reminds her of the right when he had wanted her 'blandishments', as a result of which, she had become pregnant. Anands stock-in-trade for the mind probing of his characters is in their facial expressions, thoughts and speeches. Aunt Kesaros face, for instance, reveals her anxiety about the tamarind fruit, "...Her wrinkled face was a dry brown black with the anxiety to preserve the fruit of the precious tree against all poachers." Roopa expresses her hopes and aspirations about her child's future through her unvoiced thoughts:

"Will the lack of enough nourishment turn the boy into a robber? It may know somehow that it never had enough as a child; and it may wish to revenge itself on others. But, perhaps, if it was a robber it may be like Jagga, the bandit, who robbed the rich to feed the poor and sang in the loveliest words".(*The Lost Child*, p.71) The women who visit Roopas house reveal their mind through the words they employ in their greetings. "May he lives long! "Old Kesaro said." He will give me a tunic of velvet and a silk head cloth." May he not have to beg for food, Roopa's mother-in-law said to avert the evil eye. "May he survive? A neighbour said grudgingly, "And may my own daughter-in-law become green".(*The Lost Child*, p.72)

'The Silver Bangles' is also a psycho-analytical study in character. The sight of the bangles on the sweeper girl's wrist disturbs Shrimati Gopi Goel. She at once drifts away from the kitchen to the 'jallied' window to see her husband's reaction. This gives an inkling of the house-wives suspicions of a probable love-affair between the untouchable beauty and her husband. Mrs. Goel's doubts are soon brought to the surface: She had seen, passing on his face, the ghost of a mile every time he had seen Sajani arrive. Sometimes there had been a light in his eyes which

she could not mistake for a mischievous twinkle. (*The Lost Child*, p.37)

Thereafter, a number of suggestions highlight the strains on their married life. This is indicated through indirect jestures. Mr. Goel resents his wife spying on him in a made-up verse: "Ah, between me and this bird here, there stands the shadow of despair On her part, Mrs. Goel takes recourse to her caste superiority to express her anger. She first accuses the sweeper girl of having stolen the bangles from her jewellery-box and then admonishes her for wearing them and thereby breaking all social norms:

"Get up and go out and don't you come into this house again. You have raised your head to the sky-low people, wearing silver bangles!!! Don't you know that untouchable in the South are not supposed to wear silver at all..."(*The Lost Child*, p.45) The ending of the story is as effective as is its beginning: it reveals the working of a mind ridden with superstitions. Mrs. Goel suspects that she may lose her husband to Sajani. So, she refrains from uttering the dreaded words even in her most unguarded moments. She dared not finish her harsh words, because the acknowledgement of the loss of her husband to Sajani might turn out to be the confirmation of the fact and that would be inauspicious because if you say 'death', it often comes. (*The Lost Child*, p.46)

'The Thief' incorporate yet another psychological truth the change in the behavioural pattern of a person due to a deep-seated feeling of guilt in his subconscious mind Ganesh Prasad, the protagonist of the story, has an irresistible sexual attraction for a dirty beggar woman and traces the source of his passion in a past incident when he had unjustly accused an innocent beggar of theft and had him beaten up. Thus, the hangover of an unking act against one beggar had become an undertone beneath the lust for another. His concern for the beggar woman is, in fact, a kind of atonement for guilt complex.

If the sight of the beggar woman induces in him the desire for atonement, the change in the object of his own perceptions brings about a shift in his outlook, Ganesh Prasad repairs to the balcony of his house as he attracted towards the sharp contours of the beggar woman. Here the object of his perception is "the slippery pads of her buttocks" that sway before him as she moves from the rubbish bin to the steps of the statue. However, the scene changes and the protagonist finds the beggar woman hitting her child for she has no milk in her breasts to give it. This fills him with shame. His attitude towards her undergoes a drastic change. This change from passion to compassion is brought about by a slow psychological process.

The writer often concentrates on the individual and provides insights into the pattern of man's

behaviour, is thinking and feeling. He arranges and sets forth details so as to illuminate a character or a theme in a telling moment. His *The Terrorist*, for illustration, is not only a brief account of terrorist activities indulged in by Bir Sing, but also an important comment on the Sikh Youths desire for recognition whose plan is to die uttering brave words as the bomb explodes in Parliament. One finds undertone of his resolve to be a sacrifice for his mother land:

“I die for my motherland. I become a sacrifice for it. I have tried to avenge Bharat Mata against the delivery of the British? He exulted to think that tomorrow these words of his speech would form the headlines of all the newspapers in Hindustan”. Similarly, ‘Babu Bulaki Ram’ does not merely show the relationship between Colonel Pottinger and his head-clerk, Babu Bulaki Ram an English ruler and his Indian subject, it also has its psychological implications. The colonel’s changed attitude towards his subordinate is a surprise to the latter. He had been all right before. He had got him an increase in pay before he went and had said he would recommend him for promotion to the rank of Jamadar. The key to the relationship that develops between the colonel and the head-clerk lies in the past, in the Britishers, first setting foot on the Indian soil to take upon them “the Whitemans burden”. Their “burden”, however, became whitemans India with the passage of time in which even the native had no place for themselves. These were the last days of imperial hegemony, a time when imperialism was stripped of all its glory and whatever was base in the rulers, laid bare. It was a phase of the Imperialism which was an anti-thesis of the liberal approach.

Works Cited:

Encyclopedia

1. *The Barbers Trade Union and Other Stories.* Jonathan Cape, London, 1944
2. *Lajwanti and other Stories,* Bombay Jaico, 1966
3. *Selected Stories,* Foreign Language Publishing House, Moscow, 1955
4. *The Lost Child and Other Stories,* London: J.A. Allen and Co. 1934